

Comparing the Profiles of Caesar's Heads given by the Pantelleria Marble Bust and by a Coin of 44 BC

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Abstract: Here we want to show an interesting fact concerning the profile of the Caesar's head, which is portrayed in the Pantelleria marble bust. It is the same of the portrait of Caesar given by a coin of 44 BC. The coin was struck just after Caesar's refusal of the crown offered by Mark Antony during the Lupercalia.

Keywords: Portraits of Julius Caesar, Pantelleria head, Coins.

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As told in [1], in 2003 a perfect face of Julius Caesar had been found in the Italian island of Pantelleria. Sebastiano Tusa, Thomas Schaefer (Tubingen University) and Massimo Osanna (Università della Basilicata) discovered the Caesar's head with other two marble heads of Titus and Agrippina. The perfectly preserved white marble bust found in Pantelleria is putting Caesar in a new light, according to these archaeologists, because this portrait is considered as more pristine than the other contemporary marble busts of Caesar known to exist [1].

The Pantelleria head of Caesar is dated from the reign of Claudius [2], or between the reigns of Tiberius and Claudius [3]. Of this marble head, and of its comparison to the Tusculum bust, we discussed in [4-7].

Here, we want to note an interesting fact concerning the Pantelleria head. We compare it to a portrait of Caesar given by a coin of 44 BC. The profiles of the Pantelleria bust and of the head in the coin are the same. As explained by [8], the coin was struck just after Caesar's refusal of the crown offered by Mark Antony during the Lupercalia [9].

Lupercalia was a very ancient annual festival, observed in Rome on February 15, to avert the evil spirits and purify the city [10]. Lupercalia was also called "dies Februatus", purified (literally "februated day") after the fumes of purification (see the etymology at the link <https://www.etymonline.com/word/february>).

The Lupercalia had its own priesthood, the Luperci. They were young men forming two religious collegia based on ancestry: the Quinctiliani (named after gens Quinctia) and the Fabiani (named after gens Fabia). Each college was headed by a magister. In 44 BC, a third college, the Juliani, was instituted in honour of Julius Caesar, and its first magister was Mark Antony [11]. The college of Juliani disbanded during civil wars and was not re-established in the reforms of Augustus. Descriptions of the Lupercalia of 44 BC tell that during this festival Julius Caesar refused three times a golden crown offered to him by Mark Antony.

In the Figure 1 we see, in the up/left panel, the Caesar's head in the coin struck just after Lupercalia [8] and in the down/right panel the profile of the marble head of Pantelleria. The up/right and down/left panels are giving the two images mixed in different percentage. We can see a remarkable agreement of the two profiles.

Figure 1. Profiles are the same (Images of coin and bust are used here just for scientific and cultural purposes).

Figure 2: Distances are given by the number of pixels between the end points (Images of coin and bust are used here just for scientific and cultural purposes).

From the Figure 1, it seems that even the position of the ear is the same. Therefore, let us measure the lengths of the three segments given in the Figure 2. Differences are very small, less than 3%. The posterior part of the head is different, but this is due to the fact that a crescent was inserted between the frame of the coin and the wreathed head.

After Figures 1 and 2, a possible conclusion could be the following. The Pantelleria portraiture was made according to this coin, which was struck when Caesar was alive, one month before his assassination. As a consequence, the Pantelleria bust could be considered as one of the most faithful rendering of Caesar's head.

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